

Synthesis, Characterisation and Fabrication of Hydroxyapatite Ceramics

M. K. SINHA*, S. CHATTERJEE, D. BASU and M. K. BASU

Central Glass and Ceramic Research Institute, Council of Scientific & Industrial Research, Calcutta-700 032

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In recent years much attention has been paid to hydroxyapatite as a potential biomaterial due to its chemical and crystallographic properties closely resembling those of bone and tooth minerals¹. Both dry and wet processes have been used for the synthesis of hydroxyapatite powder. However, the wet process² is generally favoured to obtain excellent powder characteristics.

Here we report the synthesis of hydroxyapatite powder from calcium hydroxide and orthophosphoric acid in a more simplified manner so that scaling-up for eventual commercial exploitation becomes less cumbersome. The powder has been characterised by XRD, ir, DTA, TGA and chemical analysis. Densification behaviour of the powder has been studied in the temperature range 1000–1250° and porous forms of hydroxyapatite ceramics have been fabricated.

Results and Discussion

The XRD pattern of as-dried powder showed that most of the peaks (3.42, 2.81, 2.777, 2.72, 1.941, 1.840 Å etc.) observed correlated closely with ASTM data of hydroxyapatite. Only two peaks (2.94 and 3.37 Å) did not correspond to hydroxyapatite peaks and they were ascribed to $\text{Ca}_3(\text{CO}_3)_2(\text{OH})_2$ and CaCO_3 respectively. In the XRD pattern of powder calcined at 1250°, these two peaks as expected were missing and instead a new peak appeared at 3.0 Å due to CaO. Besides hydroxyapatite peaks, other peaks at 3.20, 2.86 and 2.61 Å due to $\beta\text{-Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$ were also present in the XRD pattern of calcined powder. This indicated that at 1250°, there was partial decomposition of hydroxyapatite. In the ir spectra of as-dried powder, the bands at 470

(weak but sharp), 569 and 603 (strong) and 1028–1110 cm^{-1} (very strong and broad) were due to PO_4^{3-} . All these bands were present in the ir spectra of calcined powder with the difference in intensity and broadness. The as-dried powder showed a weak broad band at 3433 cm^{-1} due to adsorbed and/or structural water. Intensity of this band was much reduced in the calcined powder. The as-dried powder showed a sharp OH band for P–OH bond at 962 cm^{-1} but in the calcined powder this band was not resolved and appeared to be combined with the PO_4^{3-} band giving rise to a very broad band at 950–1150 cm^{-1} . The bands at 3570 cm^{-1} due to structural OH stretching mode and that at 630 cm^{-1} due to OH liberation mode³ were shown by both the powders. In the as-dried powder, a band at 1630 cm^{-1} was present due to adsorbed water, which disappeared in the calcined powder. The bands at 1460, 1421 and 877 cm^{-1} present in the as-dried powder were characteristics of carbonate group and as expected these bands were absent in the calcined powder. In the DTA curve of as-dried powder, a broad endothermic peak was observed at 320–430° and a small endothermic peak at 770°. The former peak was assigned to the loss of adsorbed water and the latter one to the decomposition of carbonate. TGA curve showed a weight-loss of 6.3% at 1000°. The weight-loss at 600° (5.0%) was assumed due to the loss of water, and so a weight-loss of 1.3% may possibly be accounted due to CO_2 . Comparing the chemical composition (CaO, 57.43; P_2O_5 , 36.89%) of the synthesised powder with the data corresponding to the theoretical composition (CaO, 55.8; P_2O_5 , 42.4%) of the compound, it is evident that the CaO content is higher and P_2O_5 content

is lower than the theoretical value, indicating the presence of other calcium bearing compound in the powder.

From chemical analysis, XRD, ir, DTA and TGA studies, it is evident that the synthesised powder is predominantly hydroxyapatite. Calcium carbonate is present as the minor phase as confirmed by XRD. The carbonate ion possibly came into the system from the atmosphere during the precipitation process as the reaction system was exposed to atmosphere in the present experiment. Also, the substitution of some CO_3^{2-} ions for the OH^- ions or PO_4^{3-} ions in the hydroxyapatite structure can not be ruled out completely on comparing the ir spectra of the synthesised compound with that of carbonate doped hydroxyapatite⁴.

Porosity and density data of sintered samples are given in Table 1. The test specimens on firing in the temperature range 1000–1250° showed that with increasing temperature the open porosity decreased. At 1250°, a bulk density of 2.95 g cm⁻³ with zero open porosity was achieved. The presence of $\beta\text{-Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$ in the sintered samples must have some contribution towards relatively lower value of bulk density because the theoretical density of $\beta\text{-Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$ is 3.03 and that of hydroxyapatite 3.16 g cm⁻³. Since porous ceramics with a porosity upto 60% are converted completely to natural bone tissue, we decided to prepare a porous variety also. Porous ceramics with 52% open porosity and a bulk density of 1.44 g cm⁻³ was obtained at 1250°. The pore size of the sample was between 1.7 and 0.2 μ .

TABLE I—POROSITY AND DENSITY OF SINTERED HYDROXYAPATITE

Sample	Sintering temp. °C	Soaking time h	Open porosity %	Density g cm ⁻³	Relative density %
HA-1	1000	1	40	1.52	48.1
HA-2	1100	1	34	2.02	63.9
HA-3	1200	2	8	2.79	88.3
HA-4	1250	3	0	2.95	93.4
HA-5	1250	3	52	1.44	45.6

Conclusions : Hydroxyapatite was synthesised from relatively less pure chemicals and under simple experimental conditions. The powder obtained was predominantly hydroxyapatite. Dense and porous

ceramics were made at 1250° from the synthesised powder. The fired ceramic contained $\beta\text{-Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$ and CaO in small amounts in addition to hydroxyapatite. The porous hydroxyapatite ceramics made in the present case has a potential as bone substitute material provided the ceramic is shielded from severe loading during bone in-growth.

Experimental

Powder preparation : To a vigorously stirred suspension of calcium hydroxide (L.R.; 1 mol) in distilled water (1 dm³), orthophosphoric acid (0.6 mol) solution was added dropwise at 80° over a period of ~ 2 h to produce milky gelatinous precipitate. The resulting precipitate was allowed to age for 20 h, filtered, washed with distilled water and dried at 70° for 24 h.

XRD was done using nickel-filtered CuK_α radiation in the two-theta range 10–60°. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Nicolet 5c FTIR spectrophotometer. DTA and TGA analyses were done on a MOM (Hungary) derivatograph. Calcium was estimated by EDTA titration technique and phosphate spectrophotometrically as phosphomolybdate.

Preparation of porous ceramics : The finely ground powder was mixed with polyvinyl alcohol and compacted into small discs by uniaxial pressing at 70 MPa. The compacts were fired in air in the temperature range 1000–1250° with different soaking time to determine the optimum sintering condition. To fabricate porous ceramics, in the form of bar, hydroxyapatite powder was mixed with naphthalene, pressed and fired at 1250° with a holding time 3 h.

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